

NGOs as Contributing Factor to Local Communities' Development in Rwanda. An Overview of Care International in Bugesera District

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ABSTRACT: This paper investigated the contribution of NGOs on the local communities' development in Rwanda, a case of Care International in Bugesera District (2015-2019). Specific objectives were to analyze Care International-NGO activities in Bugesera District; to assess indicators of local community development of beneficiaries from Bugesera District; to find out the relationship between Care International-NGO and local community development of its beneficiaries in Bugesera District. This study analyzed quality of data from respondents through interviews. Quantitatively the study described the contribution of NGOs on local community development in Rwanda. The correlational study was used to show the relationship between two variables. The target population 13,815 beneficiaries of Care International Rwanda, Bugesera District. Sample size was 99 respondents from Care International Rwanda, Bugesera Cluster. Sampling techniques were convenience and purposive sampling techniques. Data collection instruments used questionnaires technique. Data was analysed using the frequencies, descriptive and Pearson correlation tools in SPSS IBM 21.0 version. Findings revealed that there are different activities offered by care International-NGO in Bugesera District include strengthening the capacity for self-help for beneficiaries in Bugesera, confirmed by 90.9% respondents. Care International providing economic opportunity to beneficiaries in Bugesera, confirmed by 72.7% respondents. Findings showed different indicators of local community development of beneficiaries from Bugesera District such as an increased in agricultural and livestock productivity, confirmed by 74.7% respondents. They have food security and promote trade of agriculture products; confirmed by 71.7% respondents. An access to education for citizens and able to obtain school fees to their children, confirmed by 82.8% respondents. Findings showed the relationship between Care International-NGO and local community development of its beneficiaries in Bugesera District presented by p-value equals 0.000 which is less than Alpha (0.01). The level of relationship is $r^2 = .806^{**}$ categorized as positive and very strong correlation.

KEY WORDS: NGOs, Local Communities, Development

1. INTRODUCTION

In worldwide, Non-governmental Organizations (NGOs) show an important part in economic development of different countries. They provide facilities to society through welfare works for community development, assistance in national disasters, sustainable system development, and popular movements (Korten and Smillie, 2009). In developed countries of USA and European, NGOs aim the groups basically of the pitiable and vulnerable people with hardly some properties. The foremost tasks continue to initiate the people, create mindfulness for them and make development oriented (Korten and Smillie, 2009).

Non-governmental Organizations (NGOs) is crucial in developing countries of Africa because they frequently offer vital facilities to their citizens. NGOs in developing countries spread-out the role in speaking legal and political issues like strengthening economic and social programs, and they deliver supports in line with current Governmental strategy, acting as a sponsor to economic growth, indispensable services, employment and budget (Nyangosi, 2016).

Non-governmental organizations take a good accountability to global difficulty of enlightening environmental difficulties for the survives of families and their children; organize opinions of associate environmentally sound strategies; progress new policy opinions; and act directly in political arena as environment secure a maintainable future (Environmental NGOs, 1982). From individual perspective, poverty remains often cautious as dedicated with income capacity of the people (Chambers, 2011).

Poverty in Africa remains often considered as outcome of drought or famine. In Asia mainly due to political or bureaucratic corruption, in Europe and America due to economic slowdown or losses of jobs in periods where there remained sometime

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facing matters of poverty (Olsen, 2010). Major deficiency mitigation creativities of NGOs started directly towards well-being of the poor people through participation of government (Ruben, 2007).

Rural poverty can't stand a tenacious issue and governments all over the world have been playing the essential role that is introducing and fulfilling growth programme have been intended for wellbeing of poor rural populations (Glauben, 2012). Foremost absence of an industrialized communication system, weaker administrative set up and the distribution of information have been acting as main obstacles to full pledged of poverty mitigation programmes are helpful for overall development of country's rural poverty rank (Dorward, 2004).

In Rwanda, NGOs have increasingly developed more significant in promoting supportable development. NGOs often grasp major part of nation's political, economic or social activities, as well as assessing and speaking difficulties in both national and global issues like human, political and women's rights, economic development, democratization, immunization and vaccination, health care and the environment.

NGOs play an important role in associating with international development partners to bring resources to countries that are in need. One characteristic diverse NGOs have is that they are not interested in short-term financial goals. They continue able to devote themselves to issues which happen crossways longer time period such as temperature change, malaria stoppage or poverty decrease. NGOs often have a high degree of public trust which scripts them useful but not always sufficient middle for the concerns of humanity (Mujawayezu, 2014).

Care International Rwanda recognized in 1984 to promote an inclusive development program for the country. Initially, they absorbed on increasing rural communities which were contingent on subsistence agriculture, Care Rwanda's work has changed over time to reply in changing local needs, and concerns. Between 1994 and 1999, CARE encountered urgent desires caused by Rwandan 1994 genocide of Tutsi by focusing to its program of emergency reconstruction and reintegration. From 2000 to 2004, concentration removed to orphans and vulnerable children and HIV/AIDS (National Institute of Statistics of Rwanda, 2015/2016).

2. RESEARCH PROBLEM

Deficiency of community development remains a self-same common eye in numerous countries of the world exceptional in developing nations which remain mostly affected; and backdrop of greatest government determinations to ensure determined socio-development which are foremost channel of NGOs to emerge accompaniment for Government energies of realizing last social development for their people (Samuel, 2016). Non-Government Organizations have numerous programs, functions and roles to assist community for becoming empowered, and eventually reached sustainable development. Among of the roles of NGOs, there are micro financing, capacity building and self-reliance (Hedayat, and Ma'rof, 2010).

According to Hibbard and Tang (2004) NGOs' roles in sustainable community development remained very useful because the NGOs make equilibrium of socio-economic and conservation that influences promoting sustainable development. They discovered decentralization of the central government which aids local communities to acquire more power in order to make own decisions. Occasionally, local communities need specialists to do professional work and resources that are important for specific projects. They also assists local staff with drafting sustainable development plans which are functional under the umbrella of a Central Government Strategy. However, this study was missing the information related to communities' development as result of NGOs activities in Rwanda, and others studies that have disremember show specific link between NGOs activities and local community development in Rwanda. This indicates the scarcity of the studies in the area of Rwanda (Hibbard and Tang, 2004).

Regardless of the valuable role played by NGOs, some of communities in Africa where NGOs implement the projects, they are still suffer malnutrition and poverty. Some communities in various rural areas show effective contribution of NGO's programs to them, and they are also suffering poverty and lack necessities need for their families. It is therefore since 2005, Care International Rwanda's emphasis was on the economic and social empowerment for two key groups of population including vulnerable women, orphans and vulnerable children.

CARE International Rwanda's programming emphasizes on underlying causes of vulnerability impact Rwandan youth and low-income women by providing them with opportunities for social and financial inclusion, increasing economic empowerment, and providing liberation from gender-based violence and illiteracy among program beneficiaries. Care International in Rwanda works with community in Kamonyi, Rulindo, Musanze, Nyanza, Nyamagabe, Rubavu, Rwamagana, Nyabihu, Nyarugenge, Bugesera, Gasabo, Kicukiro (Care International report, 2019).

According to the circumstances designated above, this paper was undertaken to investigate on what are the Care International-NGO activities in Rwanda especially Bugesera District, evaluate the level of community development of Bugesera District where Care

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International implement projects, and how Care International-NGO contribute to local community development in Bugesera District. The paper carried out the contribution of Non-Government Organizations (NGOs) on local community development in Rwanda.

3. PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

General objective of this paper was to assess the contribution of NGOs on local community development in Rwanda. While this paper has three specific objectives as follows:

- i. To analyze Care International-NGO activities for beneficiaries in Bugesera District;
- ii. To find out determinants of local community development of beneficiaries in Bugesera District;
- iii. To assess the relationship between Care International-NGO and local community development of beneficiaries in Bugesera District.

4. LITERATURE REVIEW

4.1. Theoretical Framework

This section displays different theories useful to this study include change theory, and the truthful appraisal theory.

1. Change theory

The theory of change, first published by Carol Weiss (1995) well-defined modestly as a theory of how, and why an initiative works. It absorbed not just on generating knowledge about whether a project remains effective, but also on clarifying how and what methods its usages to be effective (Cox, 2009). This theory proposes the understanding on what project is challenging to achieve, how and why, project staff and evaluators continue able to monitor and measure the wanted results and compare them against the unique theory of change (Alcock, 2009).

However, this theory sprays short since project success that remains much more complex (Babbie and Mouton, 2006). It remains significant understand the success beyond fair knowing what works. Experience has exposed that blindly copying or scaling an intervention hardly ever works (Mackay, 2007).

A significant responsibility for monitoring and evaluation remains to gather sufficient knowledge and accommodating in order to forecast with some grade of self-assurance how a scheme and usual of doings strength work in a dissimilar situation, or how it needs to be agreed to get similar or better results, and hence operating project performance (Jones, 2011).

2. The Realistic Evaluation Theory

The realistic evaluation theory first was published by Pawson in 1997 brings a model placed on finding out what outcomes are formed from project involvements, how they are shaped, and what remains significant about the varying conditions in which the interventions take place. Realistic evaluation contracts with what everything for whom in what circumstances and in what respects, and how? (Pawson and Tilley, 2004). This ideal lets the surveyor to comprehend what features of an intervention make it effective or ineffective and what contextual factors are needed to replicate the intervention in other areas (Cohen and Morison, 2008). Realistic evaluation pursues to discover the contextual conditions that make interferences effective therefore developing lessons about how they yield outcomes (Fukuda-Parr and Malik, 2002).

4.2 Theoretical Literature Review

4.2.1 Non-Governmental Organizations

In New Year's rising amount of growth resources persist channel of NGOs in all sectors. NGOs are working to alleviate poverty, recover social welfare, and grow civil society to have become more dependent on global donors, foremost to a quick-tempered growth of the number of NGOs in many republics.

Global non-governmental organizations have an antiquity dating back to 1839. It has been predictable that by 1914 there were 1083 NGOs. International NGOs continued important in the anti-slavery drive and the responsibility for women's suffrage and exaggerated a peak at the time of the world withdrawing conference. Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) have amuse themselves a major role in assertive for sustainable growth at the global flat (Banks, 2012).

Demonstration gatherings have been important drivers of inter-governmental negotiations, ranging from the regulation of hazardous wastes to a global ban on land mines and the elimination of slavery. NGOs have advanced in order to complement the national efforts in if sustainable development, social services and programs to its people. NGOs in both progressive and developing countries have developed in directive to supplement disappointments of the state to effectively deliver services and development to all its citizens. It is through complementary efforts of NGOs and interest groups that good Governance can be fortified and to ensure that Government goods and services spread the grassroots, the poor, relegated, the deprived in the society in a fair and

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equitable way. The state and civil society essential to addition and enhancement all other's efforts in the developing and ability delivery agenda.

NGOs in Africa occurred typically in the 1980s though international financial institutions, donor agencies and Western Governments inspired some of the aid from African governments to civil society. NGOs stay professionally-staffed managements directing at contributing to the reduction of human suffering and to the growth of poor republics. They do this in various ways, e.g. by funding projects, attractive in service provision and capacity building, donating to awareness, and encouraging self-organization of various groups (Baccaro, 2001).

According to Desai (2005) NGOs have a significant role to play in supporting women, men and households, and probable can meet welfare. He accounted some role and functions for NGOs, such as examination supports service, awareness raising and advocacy, legal aid, and microfinance. These services benefit people achieve the ability, skill and know ledge and take control over the own lives and finally become official.

According to Stromquist (2002) famous three major drives for NGOs such as (i) service delivery (e.g. relief, welfare, basic skills); (ii) educational provision (e.g. basic skills and often critical analysis of social environments); and (iii) public policy advocacy. Baccaro (2001) shows how specific NGOs can inspire the group and approval of the poor, particularly poor women, through a combination of micro-credit, awareness-raising, training for group members, and other social services. Permission breaks the ability of individuals gain control socially, politically, economically and psychologically through (i) admission to information, knowledge and skills; (ii) decision making; and (iii) individual self-efficacy, community participation, and perceived control.

Conferring to Langran (2002) NGOs through capacity building aid to sustain community development. NGOs continue often shaped in order to enlarge the measurements of people. Additionally, NGOs are admired for endorsing community self-reliance and empowerment through supporting community-based groups and relying on participatory processes. The sustainable development has emerged over the past few decades as an important paradigm for community development. Bradshaw and Winn (2000) noted that sustainability remains secure largely in an environmental approach, particularly in the developed countries. The goal of sustainable development remains to find a balance between three pillars-social, economic and environmental of communities (Sneddon, 2000).

Hibbard and Tang, (2004) noted that importance of NGOs' roles in sustainable community development in Vietnam; one of the roles was NGOs balance the social, economic and environmental factors in encouraging sustainable development. Another important role of NGO exposed that decentralization of the central government which assistances the local communities to obtain more power in instruction to make the own decisions. Sometimes, the local communities lack specialists to do professional work and resources are significant for the particular projects. NGO contributes local staff with drafting sustainable growth plans are functional under the umbrella of a central Government policy. Finally, sustainable community development remains process-oriented, and it needs extensive community participation and trusts on network to share resources, knowledge and expertise.

NGOs show significant function in exciting sustainable community development. Sustainable community development highlights on a balance between environmental concerns and development objectives, while simultaneously enhancing local social relationships. Sustainable communities meet the economic needs of their residents, enhance and protect the environment, and promote more humane local societies (Bridger and Luloff, 1997).

Sustainable community development is attained particularly when community remains empowered. The bottom-up approach in community development would likely bring about empowerment to the community and finally sustainable community development (Finger, 1994). The bottom-up approach emphasizes community participation, grassroots movements and local decision making. Community participation and grassroots initiatives help participating decision creation and local self-reliance (Panda, 2007). In bottom-up approach, people remain cheerful to describe the own problems and enchanting ability and capacity to explain it through establishing and contributing themselves.

(a) Microfinance and Sustainable Community Development

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During the 1990s, scholars have increasingly stated to microfinance as an effective means of poverty reduction. Cheston and Khan, (2002) pointed importance of microfinance in empowerment, particularly women empowerment where microfinance is definite as efforts to recover the access to loans and to saving services for poor people (Shreiner, 2001). It is currently existence fortified as a key development strategy for promoting poverty eradication and economic empowerment. It has the possible effectively speech material poverty, the physical deprivation of goods and services and the income to attain them by granting financial services to households who are not supported by the formal banking sector (Sheraton, 2004).

According to Cheston and Khan (2002) one of the most popular forms of economic empowerment for women stays microfinance that provides credit for poor women who are usually accepted from formal credit institutions. Since the 1990s, microfinance institutions have addressed the issues of sustainability, participation and empowerment. These issues have been researched and debated by donor agencies, NGOs feminists and activists (Mahmud, 2003). However, underneath these common anxieties lie three fundamentally different methods to microfinance counting financial sustainability, feminist authorization, and poverty alleviation. All three microfinance methods have altered goals joined with varied viewpoints on how to join gender into microfinance policy and programs (Mayoux, 2000).

The microfinance approves women by beating capital in the hands and permitting them to earn an independent income and donate financially to their households and communities. This economic empowerment is estimated to generate the increased self-esteem, respect, and other forms of empowerment for women beneficiaries. Some indication display that microfinance authorize women in some parts such as growth the participation in decision making, more equitable status of women in the family and community, upsurge the political power and rights, and increase self-esteem (Cheston and Kuhn, 2002).

Well-being remains as an output of microfinance not only covers the economic indicators, but also other displays community education, environment, recreation and accessibility to social services. It is related to the quality of life (Asnarulkhadi, 2002). NGOs through microfinance support the communities to cut poverty, make jobs, and support income generation. Sustainability is connected more closely to issues of poverty and the gross inequalities of power and resources (Hamnett and Hassan, 2003).

(b) Capacity Building and Sustainable Community Development

Capacity building remains additional NGO's strategy welfares bring about sustainable free development. It remains an approach to develop the shapes independence, and it can be (i) an income to an end anywhere the purpose stays for others to take on programs. (ii) An end in itself, where the intent is enable others, from individuals through to Government departments, to have better capacity to work together to resolve difficulties (iii) a process where capacity building strategies are routinely incorporated as an vital element of effective practice (NSW Health, 2001).

Before start building capacity within agendas, practitioners essential classify pre-existing capacities like skills, structures, partnerships and resources. Frankish (2003) has calculated a number of dimensions for community capacity counting financial capacity (resources, opportunities and knowledge), human resources (skills, motivations, confidence, and relational abilities and trust) and social resources (networks, participation structures, shared trust and bonding).

UNDP (1997) introduced capacity building as the process by which individuals, groups, and organizations surge the abilities to (1) perform core functions, solve problems, define and achieve objectives; and (2) understand and contract with the expansion wants in a broad context and in a sustainable manner. Furthermore in terms of NGOs' functions, Langran (2002) capacity building as the ability of one group (NGOs) to reinforce the development abilities of additional group (local communities) through education, skill exercise and organizational support. Capacity building remains a method to development not a set of pre-determined activities. Empowerment is considered at the level of individual enablement (changes in skills, knowledge, consciousness and awareness, hope, action and beliefs in abilities to affect change) and changes in wider social structures and processes that result in increased resources and opportunities (Verity, 2007).

Furthermore, with regards to sustainability the capacity building has been recognized in much sustainable development policy as one of the key strategies for increasing the potential towards sustainable development. In the program of training women establish a small enterprise, a positive result is that women have co-operated to start the enterprise, but a sustainable outcome be contingent

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on whether women have the capacity to make it work and derive an income from it without external financial or technical assistance (Viswanath, 1991).

Building community capacities and foster empowering remain more effective ways of achieving sustainable community development than programs and success displays imposed by outside experts. The experts usually have limited knowledge and understanding of the particular context, needs and issues of a community. Local resolutions to achieve sustainable community and economic development remain therefore seen as significant outcomes of a capacity-building approach (Lennie, 2005). However, to increase people's participation in order to achieve sustainable development, many issues are considered such as skills, leadership, knowledge, physical resources and investor representativeness.

(c) Self-reliance and Sustainable Community Development

Self-reliance remains another strategy moves sustainable community development. Effective community development be seated on the foundation of self-reliance. The self-reliance is strategically located within the essence of community development and is connected to other concepts comparable mutual-help, self-help, participation of the indigenous people and rural progress. Self-reliance inspires the necessity for people to use local initiatives, the abilities and the own possessions to improve the condition.

Fonchingong (2002) pointed self-reliance remains increasingly existence accepted as *modus operandi* for community development. Self-reliance means the people trust on the own resources are independent of funds obtained outside the community. Self-reliant strategy depend on the willingness and ability of the local people to be contingent on the own available resources and technology which they can control and manage. A self-reliant strategy needs the optional use of all available human, natural and technological resources.

Although dependence on the Government may be desirable in short term, it is not a long term objective, because the goal of the community development necessity ultimately be self-reliance. Dependence on external resources principal to the loss of independence and individuality of the community. Autonomous communities can flourish in the absence of such external dependency. To attain self-reliance, community workers (e.g. NGOs) and community groups necessity learn their own potential and look for ways to creatively produce such exposed potential to habit as sources of prosperity for the growth of the community (Ife and Tesoriero, 2006).

4.3 Local Communities Development

Community development remains as together an occupation like community development worker in a local authority and a way of working with communities. Its key purpose is to build communities originated on justice, equality and mutual respect. Community development involves changing the relationships between ordinary people and people in positions of power, so that everyone can take part in the issues that affect their lives (Johnston and Beatson, 2018).

4.3.1 Indicators of Community-Level

Community-level pointers remain the events raise to population groups rather than individuals. (They designate what's happening at the community level, rather than the separate level.) Community-level indicators suggest impartial measures of outcomes. Monitoring is boiling through the community-level indicator of sales of fags in the community, rather than by polling people to find out how many cigarettes each person smoked daily. There are many places to find information on community-level indicators (Krishna, 2013).

Community-level pointers range from very specific and absorbed the rate of nighttime, single-vehicle crashes as an indicator of alcohol and substance abuse to the more subtle and indirect the amount of shelf space devoted to alcoholic beverages in local supermarkets. All the community-level indicators you use, however, should have some things in common. They should be relevant, available, and usable in practice, statistically quantifiable, logically or scientifically defensible, reliable, leading, and policy-relevant (Israel, 2008).

Community assessment is useful in community assessments for different purposes. An assessment classifies community issues and problems, for instance might trust on such indicators of the incidence of a disease or medical condition either in the community at large, or in a particular social, ethnic, or geographic group. The number of children is getting free or reduced-price school lunches or the number of schools introducing breakfast programs speak volumes about the group's economic problems or about child hunger.

Accountability is providing evidence of progress that help to maintain accountability for those who are consecutively creativities and projects. A community initiative provides more affordable housing might be measured for instance, by the number of affordable

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housing units available, or the average per-room or per-square-foot rental cost for residential property in the community. Levels of economic prosperity are dignified by looking the community's unemployment rate, average wage for workers, etc.

Evaluation. There are most likely used community-level indicators to measure progress toward the outcomes are aiming at. A substance-abuse initiative, for example, might look at admissions to treatment programs for signs of progress. Outcomes might be measured by such indicators as drug-and-alcohol-related arrests, emergency-room admissions related to substance abuse, underage drunk-driving incidents, or single vehicle, nighttime crashes.

Policy change. Community-level indicators help to determine where policy change is wanted, and whether a change in policy is consuming the desired effect. Many conditions and communities, for example, have reformed property tax laws to help seniors and lower-income people stay in the homes they have owned for many years (Mathie and Cunningham, 2010).

4.3.2 Health of Community

According to Lefevre (2000) health insurances a range of parts wellness raise and health maintenance, disease and injury prevention, detecting and addressing medical issues unique to the community, and providing health services to all who need them.

Wellness promotion and health maintenance shows healthy eating, regular exercise, and stress reduction donate to a longer and better-quality life. In addition, most people help from regular health maintenance and checking visits to health professionals, care about contact to dangerous situations or substances, etc.

Disease and injury prevention is unlike most wellness and health maintenance activities, disease and injury prevention involves taking specific measures to prevent or minimize the effects of specific diseases and conditions. Some community level indicators include the percentage of the overpopulation immunized for flu, the percentage of children recording for school with proof of all recommended inoculations, the amount of people getting regular cancer screening mammograms, pap smears, prostate antigen tests, colonoscopies, condom sales, especially among teens.

Detecting and addressing health issues unique to the community have unique health needs, stemming from the prevalence of a particular disease or condition, or from a threat to the community's health.

Providing health services to all who need them have excellent health services, but if many people continue unable to take advantage of them because of cost, difficulty of access, or some other reason than they fix those people no good.

4.3.3 Human Services and Education

Human services comprise things such as welfare; homeless and emergency aid services; job training and retraining; youth development; community-based mediation; counseling and other mental health services; violence prevention; services for seniors, and those with physical or developmental disabilities; providing support to new immigrants and language minorities; and safeguarding citizens' civil and legal rights.

Human services aimed at children and youth are several areas to focus on kids' economic conditions, their school achievement, employment, family status, use of services, etc. Some types of indicators to consider: number of families that are below the poverty line; within 150% of poverty; 200% of poverty; number of children eligible for free school lunches, subsidized child care, and other programs dependent on income.

Emergency and similar services are essentially those services necessary to sustain health and/or life for people without the resources to continue to do so for themselves. Community-level indicators can measure both the extent of the need for these services and their effectiveness such as the extent of homelessness in the community.

Second-level human services involve quality of life, rather than immediate physical survival or health, but, as a result, often address the underlying causes of problems, where emergency services, of necessity, may only address the symptoms. The percentage of people in the community who are unemployed, the number of adults enrolled in or on a waiting list for adult literacy, basic education, or majority-language-learning programs, the percentage of adults in the community lacking high school diplomas, number of child care slots available for low-income families, and availability of public transportation.

Education is usually an emphasis on publicly-funded or otherwise universally-available education, so that private schools and colleges are not part of the mix, except insofar as they offer scholarships or the equivalent. Many private schools in smaller towns, for instance, offer free tuition to local youth who can meet admission standards such as number of slots in affordable pre-school programs head start, subsidized pre-school slots for low-income families, school district early education programs, school status like dropout rate, number of children in grades 3-12 more than one grade level behind in reading or math.

Economic may be observing at the economic development of the community as a whole or that of specific groups within it. Community-level indicators consider the number of new businesses starting annually, the number of business failures or bankruptcies each year, the average income level, the average education level, the unemployment rate, local revenue from taxes and fees, the percentage of businesses and industries are locally owned, the average commute to work for local inhabitants, the

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default rate on local business and mortgage loans, average housing prices, the percentage of residents own the own homes, the percentage of people who are below the poverty line, homeless, or receiving public assistance, and the percentage of children getting free school lunches.

Social/demographic include how people tell one another in the community, and what people do as groups to participate in the community and hold it composed. Demographic indicators define the community's residents ethnic, gender, age, and racial diversity, the geographic distribution, etc. Social indicators remain significant in thoughtful how people are linked to one another, as well as how they sometimes distinguish against or distrust one another.

Cultural is used to refer to both culture in the sense of arts, entertainment, and knowledge (which are, in fact, the passing on of the valued products of the majority culture), and "culture" in the sense of the customs and world view of the various ethnic, racial, and religious groups in the community.

4.3.4 Public Safety

Since 2001, public safety in many municipalities at least, has come to more than police protection or earthquake-proof buildings. It means security from terrorism, which in turn, increases issues of privacy and civil rights when protection grows vigorous. As with health, the most effective way to ensure public safety is to take preventive measures long before any threat exists. In the examples of community-level indicators, they offer events of prevention of the balance between safety and civil liberties and of traditional public safety activities.

5. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWOR

The conceptual framework is derived from the theoretical framework and linked with the current study and followed by a paradigm that links the variables by giving the direction of how the researcher operationalizes the variables by relationships or comparison.

Therefore, in order to resolve the problem, this paper recognized the relationship between independent variable in terms of NGOs activities, and dependent variable in terms of local community development.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Source: *Research Conceptualization, (2021)*

6. METHODOLOGY

This paper remained non-experimental research, and that reason it applied cross-sectional survey design. That was to say qualitative and quantitative approaches were applied in this paper. This paper directed 13,815 beneficiaries supported by Care International in Bugesera District. Questionnaires used as self-administered questionnaire to collect information from 99 respondents in the beneficiaries of Care International that related to research project. It comprised a number of questions spoke to the respondents.

6.1 Sample size and Sampling technique

The sample size of this paper remains 99 respondents from beneficiaries of Care International Rwanda especially Bugesera Cluster. Convenience sampling was applied in this paper to measure the perception of their image in the use of NGOs services and accessing the activities. Data is collected from potential respondents to understand their specific opinions for NGOs. This paper used purposive sampling technique, the researcher ordered the purposive sampling to choose the respondents from beneficiaries. It was purposive sampling also known as judgment in which the study choose the members of population to participate in the paper.

6.2 Data c Analysis Procedures

Data processing explains how data was obtained from respondents of Care International Rwanda was edited, coded and made the statistical tables by using various methods. The methods were used to analyze data of this research remains descriptive statistical

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method described the frequency, percentages, and cumulative percentage of data from Care International Rwanda. The study used correlation coefficient analysis method to identify relationship between NGOs and community development

7. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Data are analyzed quantitatively using SPSS IBM 21.0 version, and results were presented and interpreted in accordance with research objectives. This paper achieved three specific objectives including analysis of Care International-NGO activities in Bugesera District; assess the indicators of local community development of beneficiaries from Bugesera District; and find out the relationship between Care International-NGO and local community development of its beneficiaries in Bugesera District. Questionnaires were distributed to 99 respondents; and they were given two weeks of responding the questions. Findings indicated participation rate of 100.0% in responding to the questions. This helped the researcher to continue with editing, recording, coding, and make statistical tables using SPSS Software of analysis. Gender distribution of respondents showed that there is both males and females in the beneficiaries of Care International-Rwanda, Bugesera District, and also females are more than males. This was justified by 40 (i.e. 40.4%) respondents who are males, while 59 (i.e. 59.6%) respondents are females. Having both sexes in the project beneficiaries is an indicator which is showing that the activities of Care International-Rwanda benefitted by both categories in Bugesera District as to support local community development.

7.1 Activities and services of Care International Rwanda to beneficiaries from Bugesera District

Table 1. Perception of respondents about the activities offered by Care International to the beneficiaries in Bugesera District

Activities of Care International Rwanda, Bugesera District	SA		A		N		D		SD	
	fi	%								
Strengthening capacity for self-help for beneficiaries in Bugesera.	21	21.2	69	69.7	5	5.1	2	2.0	2	2.0
Providing economic opportunity for beneficiaries in Bugesera.	34	34.3	38	38.4	11	11.1	16	16.2	0	0.0
Delivering relief in emergencies.	35	35.4	51	51.5	2	2.0	6	6.1	5	5.1
Influencing policy decisions at all levels.	37	37.4	44	44.4	13	13.1	0	0.0	5	5.1
Addressing discrimination in all its forms.	36	36.4	34	34.3	0	0.0	11	11.1	18	18.2
Facilitating community involvement.	13	13.1	51	51.5	13	13.1	17	17.2	5	5.1
Providing equity and special needs.	31	31.3	32	32.3	8	8.1	17	17.2	11	11.1
Elaborating early childhood care development.	47	47.5	37	37.4	0	0.0	9	9.1	6	6.1
Facilitating Girls education in Bugesera District.	36	36.4	52	52.5	6	6.1	5	5.1	0	0.0
Playing role in teacher development and education leadership.	14	14.1	36	36.4	22	22.2	23	23.2	4	4.0
Providing service orientation like provision of health, family planning or education services.	34	34.3	52	52.5	8	8.1	5	5.1	0	0.0
Helping the local people to be involved particularly in the implementation of a project through contributing cash, tools, land, materials, and labour.	20	20.2	48	48.5	8	8.1	11	11.1	12	12.1
Empowering orientation that aims help poor people develop a clearer understanding of the social, political and economic factors affecting their lives.	38	38.4	53	53.5	5	5.1	3	3.0	0	0.0
Involving in charitable orientation on a top-down effort with little participation or input by beneficiaries.	33	33.3	53	53.5	5	5.1	0	0.0	8	8.1

Source: Primary data, (November, 2021)

According to the findings shown above, Care International was strengthening the capacity for self-help for beneficiaries in Bugesera, confirmed by 90.9% respondents who strongly agreed and agreed. Care International providing economic opportunity to

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beneficiaries in Bugesera, confirmed by 72.7% respondents. Delivering relief in emergencies to beneficiaries in Bugesera, confirmed by 86.9% respondents. Influencing policy decisions at all levels, confirmed by 81.8% respondents. Addressing discrimination in all its forms, confirmed by 70.7% respondents.

They have facilitated community involvement, confirmed by 64.6% respondents. Providing equity and special needs, confirmed by 63.6% respondents. Elaborating early childhood care development, confirmed by 84.8% respondents. Facilitating Girls education in Bugesera District, confirmed by 88.9% respondents. Playing role in teacher development and education leadership, confirmed by 50.5% respondents. Providing service orientation like provision of health, family planning or education services, confirmed by 86.9% respondents. Care International was helping the local people to be involved particularly in the implementation of a project through contributing cash, tools, land, materials, and labour, confirmed by 68.7% respondents. It is empowering orientation that aims help poor people develop a clearer understanding of the social, political and economic factors affecting their lives, confirmed by 91.9% respondents. Involving in charitable orientation on a top-down effort with little participation or input by beneficiaries, confirmed by 86.9% respondents.

According to CARE International (2013) CARE Rwanda's Programs use a number of robust and proven 'models' to deliver their goals. For us, a model is an approach that not only delivers an impact, but is also simple, sustainable and cost effective enough to be replicated and scaled-up, not only by CARE but also by partners and other actors, including by the Government where appropriate. They work hard to document our models and to share them with all stakeholders so that they can be understood, adapted and adopted. CARE has become a change agent by modelling "climate smart" policies, plans and practices at the highest levels of our confederation. CARE is effectively advancing a pro-poor approach to carbon finance programming that reduces poverty, secures rights, enhances gender equality and supports adaptation to climate change while ensuring real mitigation. CARE is effectively helping the world's most vulnerable people adapt to the impacts of climate change, and we are contributing to global learning processes about adaptation especially with regards to empowering poor women. CARE is modelling a) how climate change policies, strategies and programmes can integrate social justice, gender equality and empowerment, and b) how women's empowerment and other programmes can integrate the additional challenges posed by climate change.

7.2 Findings on Indicators of Local Community Development in Bugesera District

Findings of the paper show that indicators of local community development in Bugesera District that included by an increased in agricultural and livestock productivity; having food security and promote trade of agriculture products; creation and enhancement of sustainable off-farm employment; increase inputs for economic expansion and protect entrepreneurs against business risks; an access to education for citizens and able to obtain school fees to their children; having cleaned water and hygiene and sanitation; and having transport means like bicycles, Moto-bicycle, or car; able to build their own house or shelters; having home animals like cows, hens, goats, sheep, etc. accessing to affordable electricity and transport infrastructure as support to economic transformation as detailed in table 2.

Table 2. Perception of respondents about the development of beneficiaries of Care International in Bugesera District

Indicators of development of beneficiaries joint Care International	SA		A		N		D		SD	
	fi	%								
An increased in agricultural and livestock productivity.	21	21.2	53	53.5	13	13.1	12	12.1	0	0.0
Having food security and promote trade of agriculture products.	39	39.4	32	32.3	9	9.1	11	11.1	8	8.1
Creation and enhancement of sustainable off-farm employment.	3	3.0	66	66.7	6	6.1	22	22.2	2	2.0
Increase inputs for economic expansion and protect entrepreneurs against business risks.	42	42.4	22	22.2	0	0.0	13	13.1	22	22.2
An access to education for citizens and able to obtain school fees to their children.	36	36.4	46	46.5	3	3.0	9	9.1	5	5.1
Having cleaned water and hygiene and sanitation.	43	43.4	56	56.6	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Having transport means like bicycles, Moto-bicycle, or car.	8	8.1	40	40.4	3	3.0	11	11.1	37	37.4
Able to build their own house or shelters.	34	34.3	49	49.5	8	8.1	0	0.0	8	8.1

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Having home animals like cows, hens, goats, sheep, etc.	22	22.2	74	74.7	3	3.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
Presenting a decrease in unemployment rate.	57	57.6	36	36.4	3	3.0	3	3.0	0	0.0
Homelessness prevention.	65	65.7	21	21.2	3	3.0	0	0.0	10	10.1
Neighborhood stabilization.	36	36.4	52	52.5	3	3.0	8	8.1	0	0.0
Domestic violence community reduction.	38	38.4	37	37.4	9	9.1	15	15.2	0	0.0
Cultural development among citizens.	33	33.3	52	52.5	2	2.0	6	6.1	6	6.1
Receiving monthly revenue or income at given period from business.	38	38.4	39	39.4	0	0.0	16	16.2	6	6.1
Poverty reduction for beneficiaries in Bugesera District.	35	35.4	35	35.4	0	0.0	9	9.1	20	20.2
Able to pay health insurance.	11	11.1	55	55.6	12	12.1	15	15.2	6	6.1
Accessing to affordable electricity and transport infrastructure as support to economic transformation.	32	32.3	32	32.3	8	8.1	15	15.2	12	12.1
Accessing to market information and technology innovations for production.	32	32.3	49	49.5	10	10.1	6	6.1	2	2.0
Help for accessing to energy of peat, biogas, solar for improved welfare and environmental protection.	28	28.3	48	48.5	9	9.1	9	9.1	5	5.1

Source: Primary data, (2021)

There are an increase in agricultural and livestock productivity, confirmed by 74.7% respondents. They have food security and promote trade of agriculture products; confirmed by 71.7% respondents. Creation and enhancement of sustainable off-farm employment, confirmed by 69.7% respondents. Increase inputs for economic expansion and protect entrepreneurs against business risks, confirmed by 64.6% respondents. An access to education for citizens and able to obtain school fees to their children, confirmed by 82.8% respondents. Having cleaned water and hygiene and sanitation, confirmed by all 100.0% respondents. Having transport means like bicycles, Moto-bicycle, or car, confirmed by 48.5% respondents. Able to build their own house or shelters, confirmed by 83.8% respondents. Beneficiaries have home animals like cows, hens, goats, sheep, etc., confirmed by 97.0% respondents. Presenting a decrease in unemployment rate, confirmed by 93.9% respondents. Homelessness prevention, confirmed by 86.9% respondents. Neighborhood stabilization, confirmed by 88.9% respondents. Domestic violence community reduction, confirmed by 75.8% respondents. Cultural development among citizens, confirmed by 85.9% respondents. Receiving monthly revenue or income at given period from business, confirmed by 77.8% respondents. Poverty reduction for beneficiaries in Bugesera District, confirmed by 70.7% respondents. Able to pay health insurance, confirmed by 66.7% respondents. Accessing to affordable electricity and transport infrastructure as support to economic transformation, confirmed by 64.6% respondents. Accessing to market information and technology innovations for production, confirmed by 81.8% respondents.

CARE international's climate vulnerability and capacity analysis (CVCA) model starts awareness about how climate change policies, strategies, and programs assimilate social justice, gender equality, and empowerment, and how women's empowerment and other programs can integrate the additional challenges posed by climate change. It highlights the dramatic affects that climate change specifically has on vulnerable groups who make up some of the poorest communities in the world. By using local knowledge and scientific data, the Climate Change Strategic Plan approaches methods for educating vulnerable groups on how climate change affects their livelihoods as an individual and community, and the steps that can be taken to adapt to the altering environment. It collects information to better understand what local and national institutions have a role in shaping vulnerable people's adaptive capacity so that they can successfully overcome climate change.

CARE International (CI) members and country offices have begun factoring the impacts of climate change into the design of women's empowerment and other programmes with attention to human conditions, social position and enabling environment; CI members, country offices and key implementing partners have greater knowledge and skills to main-stream a social justice and gender equality perspective into their climate change policies, strategies and programmes; CARE's action-research and communications campaigns have made a significant contribution to key stakeholders' understanding of, and attention to, the role of women and other marginalised people in building household, community and social adaptive capacity;

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CARE has become recognized as a leader in promoting the interests and rights of women in CC advocacy and programming; and PECCN has assessed its contribution to social justice, gender equality and empowerment in annual reports to its Steering Committee. The specific policy change objectives remain the international community has reached and is implementing a fair, ambitious and binding agreement on climate change that contributes to sustainable development, resilience and food security while respecting, protecting and promoting the rights of poor women and other vulnerable people. Climate change policies, guidelines and funding mechanisms in key countries are contributing to sustainable development, resilience and food security while respecting, protecting and promoting the rights of poor women and other vulnerable people.

The specific programme objectives are CARE and key implementing partners have increased capacity (including skills, expertise and resources) to advocate for climate change policies benefitting poor women and other highly vulnerable people at international, regional and national levels, with a particular focus on adaptation, REDD, and gender equality. CARE is a significant contributor to new knowledge and evidence-based recommendations for gender-transformative adaptation and reduced emissions from deforestation and forest degradation (REDD) policies.

CARE and local partners have developed a portfolio of high quality community based adaptation projects that demonstrate best practices, especially with regards to enhancing gender equality; CARE programme quality in climate-sensitive sectors (such as water and agriculture) has been improved through the integration of gender-transformative climate change adaptation; CARE and key implementing partners have increased capacity (including skills, expertise and resources) to develop and implement CBA projects, as well as integrate adaptation into projects in climate-sensitive sectors; and CARE has become a substantial contributor to global learning processes about adaptation, especially with regards to the importance and practice of gender-transformative approaches. CARE and local partners have developed a portfolio of high quality carbon finance projects that demonstrate best practices especially with regards to reducing poverty, securing rights, enhancing gender equality and supporting adaptation to climate change; CARE has played a leading role in the development of REDD+ social and environmental standards, and these standards are clearly influencing the policy and practice of national REDD programmes to more effectively reduce poverty, secure rights, and enhance gender equality;

CARE has established an effective quality and risk management mechanism for its carbon finance projects based on internal and third-party standards; CARE and key implementing partners have increased capacity (including skills, expertise and resources) to develop and implement pro-poor carbon finance projects; and CARE has become a substantial contributor to global knowledge and learning about carbon finance programming especially with regards to reducing poverty, securing rights, enhancing gender equality and supporting adaptation to climate change.

CARE members are progressively reducing their environmental impact in-line with shared expectations and common policies, CARE members are integrating a gendered perspective on climate change into their long-range organisational and operational plans, and PECCN has become a CI-wide "Centre of Expertise" with inclusive, transparent and accountable governance structures, policies and practices.

7.3 The relationship between Care International-NGO and local community development of its beneficiaries in Bugesera District

The findings below show the relationship between the activities offered by Care International-NGO and local community development of its beneficiaries in Bugesera District. In correlating two variables using Pearson Correlation analysis, the research got table 3 as follows:

Table 3. Correlation Coefficient Test

	Care International-NGO Activities in Bugesera	Local Community Development in Bugesera
Care International-NGO Activities in Bugesera	1	.806**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	99
Local Community Development in Bugesera District	.806**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	99

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

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Table 3 presents p-value which equals to 0.000 which is less than Alpha (0.01). This is an indicator of the relationship between Care International-NGO Activities in Bugesera and local community development in Bugesera District. The level of relationship remains $r^2 = .806^{**}$ as revealed by the above table, it is located in interval $[-.75 - +1]$ characterized as positive and very strong correlation. This helps to confirm that there is significant the relationship between Care International-NGO and local community development of its beneficiaries in Bugesera District.

8. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

The results from the study was done that the main projects implemented by CARE International since 2015-2019 in Bugesera district; CARE Rwanda's OVC program is built on a number of strong, well-tested models. These models involve of Nkundabana, early childhood development, village and savings loans, and community score card which have been developed and refined based on past experience of CARE Rwanda and others, as well as theoretical research. CARE has played a leading role in the development of social and environmental standards, and these standards are clearly inducing the policy and practice of national rogrammes to more effectively reduce poverty, protected rights, and improve gender equality;

CARE has established an effective quality and risk management mechanism for its carbon finance projects based on internal and third-party standards; CARE and key implementing partners have increased capacity (including skills, expertise and resources) to develop and implement pro-poor carbon finance projects; and CARE has become a substantial contributor to global knowledge and learning about carbon finance programming especially with regards to reducing poverty, securing rights, enhancing gender equality and supporting adaptation to climate change. CARE members are progressively reducing their environmental impact in-line with shared expectations and common policies, CARE Members are integrating a gendered perspective on climate change into their long-range organizational and operational plans, and PECCN has become a CI-wide Centre of Expertise with inclusive, transparent and accountable governance structures, policies and practices. As conclusion, according to the findings obtained in the above, the objectives of this study were achieved, problem was solved and research questions were answered.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the researcher has formulated the recommendations. There is therefore a need for NGOs like CARE International should make the use of change that requires to develop reference points on what needs to be accomplished and what needs to be done to accomplish the said plans. The NGOs can also make use of forecasting to regulate the type of projects to pursue and assess the potential of the ongoing projects.

It is important to be specific in the hazards, and to ensure that the issues identified remain actually hazards. Participants recognize conditions such as the food insecurity as hazards. It is up to the facilitator to ask the group to break down these conditions to determine if they are caused by hazards (e.g. food insecurity may be the result of a drought, which is a hazard). Similarly, some groups may identify scarcity of resources, such as lack of money, as a hazard. In this case, it should be determined whether the lack of a resource remain the result of a hazard, or in some cases, whether the resource is added to the list of priority resources identified in the previous step. Otherwise, CARE International remains good non-government organization, should if possible to expand their activities and services to rest of districts to help people to enhance their wellbeing.

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